

The College Climate Campaign

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In recent years consumers are using more electricity, water and gas in their everyday life. Especially younger people use more than an average person; according to studies up to 20 % more (Rasmussen, 2012). A campaign in 3 DTU-dormitories addressed this problem, trying to reduce the consumption for around 1000 people living in the three dormitories P.O.P, Bergsøe and Trørød. The overall goal of the campaign was a reduction of 15 %. The most important goal though was to encourage the residents to think about environmental issues. By doing so in their own home, the hope was that they would bring the learnings with them in their future career, which is an engineering career for most residents. Another goal was that the campaign should be a kick-starter for other dormitories wishing to do the same. With potentially 40.000 residents living in dormitories in Denmark, spreading a project like this could have an enormous impact on consumption, which is the easiest way to save energy.

The campaign was, amongst others, supported by some of the biggest engineering firms in Denmark, such as Dong Energy, Rambøll, Alectia, Haldor Topsøe and Grontmij. Furthermore Lyngby-Taarbæk- and Gladsaxe Municipality supported the project, along with Tuborfondet.

The result of the campaign was a reduction in the use of electricity, water and gas, averaging 11 % compared to the year before. The overall conclusion is that an energy saving campaign made by students for students is an effective tool for reducing the consumption.